

Scheme 1

In this proposed mechanism the radical anion 1 is formed from one molecule of an aldehyde by taking an electron. The molecule of other aldehyde also takes an electron to form a radical anion 2, which subsequently loses a hydrogen free radical to evolve an enolate anion 3. Thereafter anion 3 combines with carbon free radical 1 and by losing one electron rearranges to form anion 4. By releasing an electron 4 converts into a free radical 5 and then it combines with earlier lost hydrogen free radical to form the product aldol 6, which on subsequent dehydration forms α,β -unsaturated aldehydes 7.

It is evident from the Table 1, in which electrolysis were carried out at different potentials in the given range

Table 1. Current-potential data of electrolysis as recorded by potentiostat

Entry	Aldehydes	Potential (V)	Current (A)	Yield (%)
1	Acetaldehyde	1.55	0.20-0.26	55
2	Benzaldehyde with acetaldehyde	1.58	0.30-0.35	60
3	<i>p</i> -Anisylaldehyde with acetaldehyde	2.01	0.29-0.34	80
4	<i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde with acetaldehyde	2.00	0.35-0.75	80
5	<i>p</i> -Bromobenzaldehyde with acetaldehyde	2.15	0.80-0.85	80

that the reaction starts at 1.55 V but the yield increases with increasing potential and we obtained the maximum yield at the potential 2.00 V. Above the potential 2.00 V reaction continues but the yield decreases with increasing potential and above 2.20 V reaction checks out. All the

electrolysis were carried out at their corresponding reduction potential and were completed in an hour. After an hour no reduction product was seen to diffuse in the bulk.

In this system the reaction takes place at the room temperature in the potential range 1.55-2.20 V, but the specific potential for the reaction is found to be approximately 2.00 V. The observations recorded in these reactions are given in Table 1.

The products were extracted in the chloroform layer by simple solvent extraction after diluting the reaction solution with double distilled water. Thereafter the chloroform was easily evaporated at low temperature 30-35 °C. Then the purity of products were checked from thin layer chromatography. All the products were coloured and entirely different from the starting aldehydes. It is obvious from the studies that the electroinduced aldol formation provides a good method of electroorganic synthesis of aldol or α,β -unsaturated aldehydes and it is a simple and ecofriendly synthetic method and hence a part of Green Chemistry.

Analysis of the products :

All the products are known compounds and were analyzed by chemical methods as well as by spectral studies.

Chemical analysis : The products were analysed for unsaturation by bromine-water test.

Spectral analysis :

IR spectra in KBr were recorded on Shimadzu 8201 PC IR spectrophotometer ($4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$). ^1H NMR (200, 300 MHz) and ^{13}C NMR (300, 300 MHz) spectra were measured at room temperature on Bruker 300 FT spectrometer instruments, with tetramethylsilane (TMS) (δ 0.0 ppm, ^1H NMR spectra) and CDCl_3 (δ 77.0 ppm, ^{13}C NMR spectra) or C_6D_6 (δ 127.8 ppm, ^{13}C NMR) as internal standards. Carbon multiplities were assigned by DEPT techniques. Microanalyses were carried out in the Elementar Vario EL III.

Crotonaldehyde : Light yellow colour (Found : C, 77.10; H, 8.42. Calcd. for $\text{C}_4\text{H}_6\text{O}$: C, 77.47; H, 8.57%); mol. wt. 70; b.p. 104°C ; IR ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 1650 (C=C), 1723 (C=O), 2868 (aliphatic C-H), 3055 (=C-H); ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3/TMS) : δ 1.37 (3H, d, J 6.0 Hz, CH_3), 5.25 (1H, t, J 6.0 Hz, CH), 6.2 (1H, d, J 6.0 Hz, CH), 9.8 (1H, d, J 6.0 Hz, CHO); ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3/TMS) : δ 15.9, 123.3 (=C), 191.6 (CHO).

Cinnamaldehyde : Orange colour (Found : C, 81.35; H, 5.95. Calcd. for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{O}$: C, 81.81; H, 6.06%); mol. wt. 132; b.p. 252°C ; IR ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 680, 810, 960, 1660 (C=C), 1695 (C=O), 2865 (aliphatic C-H), 3033 (=C-H); ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3/TMS) : δ 5.5 (1H, d, J 6.0 Hz, CH), 6.9 (1H, m, J 6.0 Hz, CH), 6.96–7.26 (5H, dd, J 2.6 and 5.6 Hz, Ar-H), 9.5 (1H, d, J 6.0 Hz, CHO); ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3/TMS) : δ 123.3 (=C), 128.5 (Ar-H), 192.1 (CHO).

***p*-Methoxycinnamaldehyde :** Dark yellowish (Found : C, 73.94; H, 6.11. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2$: C, 74.07; H, 6.17%); mol. wt. 162; m.p. $44\text{--}46^\circ\text{C}$; IR ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 735–860 (*o,p*-disubstituted benzene), 1660 (C=C), 1690 (C=O), 2815 (O- CH_3), 2850 (aliphatic C-H), 2865 (aliphatic C-H), 3030 (=C-H), 3040 (Ar-C-H), 3336 (NH); ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3/TMS) : δ 3.45 (3H, s, OCH_3), 5.5 (1H, d, J 6.0 Hz, CH), 6.9 (1H, t, J 6.0 Hz, CH), 7.06–7.27 (4H, dd, J 2.6 and 5.6 Hz, Ar-H), 9.6 (1H, d, J 6.0 Hz, CHO); ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3/TMS) : δ 48.5 (OCH_3), 123.3 (=C), 125.5, 128.4, 129.2, 137.7 (ArC), 192.3 (CHO).

***p*-Hydroxycinnamaldehyde :** Pale yellow (Found : C,

72.47; H, 5.40. Calcd. for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{O}_2$: C, 72.97; H, 5.40%); mol. wt. 148; m.p. 160°C ; IR ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 735–860 (*o,p*-disubstituted benzene), 1050 (OH), 1660 (C=C), 1690 (C=O), 2865 (aliphatic C-H), 3035 (=C-H), 3045 (Ar-C-H), 3640 (phenolic); ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3/TMS) : δ 2.6 (1H, s, OH), 5.5 (1H, d, J 6.0 Hz, CH), 6.9 (1H, t, J 6.0 Hz, CH), 7.05–7.28 (4H, dd, J 2.6 and 5.6 Hz, Ar-H), 9.5 (1H, d, J 6.0 Hz, CHO); ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3/TMS) : δ 123.3 (=C), 125.5, 128.4, 129.2, 137.7 (Ar-C), 191.8 (CHO).

***p*-Bromocinnamaldehyde :** Brown colour (Found : C, 72.47; H, 5.40; Br, 35.18. Calcd. for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{O}_2\text{Br}$: C, 47.36; H, 2.36; Br, 35.08%); mol. wt. 228; m.p. $66\text{--}68^\circ\text{C}$; IR ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 585 (Ar-Br), 735–860 (*o,p*-disubstituted benzene), 1660 (C=C), 1693 (C=O), 2865 (aliphatic C-H), 3040 (=C-H), 3045 (Ar-C-H); ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3/TMS) : δ 5.6 (1H, d, J 6.0 Hz, CH), 6.9 (1H, t, J 6.0 Hz, CH), 7.05–7.26 (4H, dd, J 2.6 and 5.6 Hz, Ar-H), 9.8 (1H, d, J 6.0 Hz, CHO); ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3/TMS) : δ 123.3 (=C), 125.6, 128.4, 129.3, 137.8 (Ar-C), 191.8 (CHO).

Experimental

Reaction mixture : The reaction mixture contains the 50 mL of 0.1 M solution of starting material using dimethyl formamide (DMF) as aprotic solvent + 50 mL of the 0.1 M aqueous solution of KCl, which is used as supporting electrolyte.

All the aldehydes, DMF, mercury, KCl and chloroform were of AnalaR grade. Water used was double distilled.

Electrolysis : The electrolysis were carried out at controlled potential in four-necked 250 mL capacity bottle which is designed in our laboratory. For controlled potential electrolysis, we have used conventional three electrode cell assembly with platinum¹⁰⁻¹² (flattened sheet of dimension 1.0 cm \times 0.5 cm) as working as well as counter electrode. These Pt-electrodes are surrounded from one side with glass material and saturated calomel electrode (SCE) is used as reference electrode.

Conclusion :

It is obvious from the studies that the electroinduced aldol formation provides a good method of electroorganic synthesis of aldol or α,β -unsaturated aldehydes and it is simple and ecofriendly synthetic method and hence a part of Green Chemistry.

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